

Systematic Review of HIPAA and Privacy Regulations in Correctional Facilities with a Focus on HIV-Positive Inmates

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Abstract

The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act is a federal law that was signed into law in 1996. The purpose of this is to ensure the safety and privacy of sensitive health information from being disclosed without the knowledge of the patient. This is also made true in correctional facilities. Inmates have the same HIPAA rights as civilians, like the minimum necessary standard. Covered entities under HIPAA include any health plan, healthcare clearinghouse, or healthcare provider communicating Protected Health Information (PHI) electronically. This paper reviewed the privacy regulations in correctional facilities and the stigma surrounding HIV. I described how the minimum necessary utilizes protected health information for intended purposes and under what circumstances law enforcement can receive protected health information. In addition, I focused on the stigma surrounding HIV-positive inmates and how the segregation of HIV-positive inmates is a breach of confidentiality. Methods used are MeSH search on the National Library of Medicine to identify papers that present data on privacy regulations in prison. We also utilized a public dataset on staff stigma attitudes surrounding HIV in correctional facilities and visually summarized the data.

Introduction

Healthcare within correctional facilities presents unique challenges between law enforcement, healthcare, and individual privacy. As the United States deals with one of the highest incarceration rates^{1,20}, the need to balance between maintaining the security of correctional institutions and upholding the fundamental right to healthcare privacy has become increasingly critical. The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), enacted in 1996, established a framework for safeguarding individuals' medical information in various healthcare settings. However, applying HIPAA regulations within correctional facilities presents a complex and evolving area of concern. HIV segregation in prison systems is illegal discrimination and a breach of confidentiality. Not only is it a violation of human rights, but it also breaks the US guidelines for the management of HIV in prison.^{9,18}

Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 (HIPAA)

In 1996, the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act was signed into law to protect the exchange of health information. This allowed patients to control who they released their personal health information to.² Organizations that do not comply with HIPAA will face penalties, motivating them to ensure privacy. This law creates a standard for all organizations that handle sensitive medical records. The privacy rule, enacted in 2000, sets a standard for protected health information (PHI). In the privacy rule, an inmate hospital is not required to get authorization or consent from the patient before using or disclosing their PHI for treatment, payment, or healthcare operations.⁴ Then in 2003, the Privacy Rule became effective allowing patients the right to personal health information and setting limits on how their information is being used.³ The privacy rule also allowed “covered entities” to disclose and share PHI

electronically with transactions, however, this cannot be done without the patient's authorization. HIPAA could easily be broken by simply entering the incorrect patient's chart or separating patients based on diagnosis. This act unintentionally discloses the status of inmates without their consent. With the increase in electronic health record use, we need to be careful in how we transmit medical records.

Covered Entities

Covered Entities, a crucial part of the privacy rule, are organizations or individuals who are required to follow HIPAA laws. These organizations include healthcare providers, health plans, insurance, and healthcare clearinghouses transmitting electronic health information. A decision tool is offered to help determine if an individual or organization is considered a covered entity.⁵ Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services provides this tool for those who are not sure if they fall under covered entities. The decision tool contains questions like "Does the person, business, or agency furnish, bill, or receive payment for health care in the normal course of business?" and "Does the business or agency process, or facilitate the processing of, health information from nonstandard format or content into standard format or content or from standard format or content into nonstandard format or content?"⁸ Covered Entities are allowed to disclose patient's personal health information for treatment, payment, or healthcare operations purposes without having the patient's authorization.¹² In HIPAA's 45 CFR Part 164 Subpart C, covered entities are required to conduct an assessment for potential risks and vulnerability to the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of PHI held by the covered entities. The goal of this assessment is to identify weak areas where the organization's protected health information (PHI) could be at risk.⁵ However, HIPAA permits covered entities to transmit PHI without consent in specific situations, such as treatment, public health activities, court orders, subpoenas, and law enforcement purposes.⁵

Principle of Minimum Necessity

The principle of Minimum Necessity is the standard for protecting PHI and requires covered entities to make an effort to limit the request of PHI to only what is necessary after receiving permission. An exception exists for health-care providers sharing information for treatment, at the request of the HHS Secretary, for reasons required by law, or when sharing information with the individual who is the patient or consumer.⁷ HIPAA and 42 CFR Part 2 establish a minimum standard for protecting and securing PHI. State laws also have provisions allowing courts to obtain health-care information from covered entities in response to a judicial order.¹² Covered entities are instructed to disclose only information specifically authorized by the court order, aligning with the principle of minimum necessity. Courts can receive PHI under specific conditions outlined in these laws, with an emphasis on obtaining only the information authorized by a court order. Only those who require access to inmate health information to perform their job duties should be granted access. This includes healthcare workers, administrative workers, and other relevant staff. Prison guards, for example, may not require detailed medical histories, so access to such information is limited to those directly involved in healthcare provision.

Methods

In my research, I used a structured approach to identify and analyze relevant literature about privacy regulations in correctional facilities, particularly regarding the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). To start, I utilized the academic database PubMed, a reputable source for scholarly articles, and we focused on articles indexed with specific MeSH

(Medical Subject Headings) terms. Our MeSH search will include subject headings "HIPAA", "Prison", "Correctional Facilities", "Privacy", "Protected Health Information", "Health Information Exchange" and "HIV", ensuring a systematic search of the topic.

To ensure the relevance of the articles, we will examine the search results and focus on papers specifically addressing correctional facilities within the United States. This geographical constraint is important as the legal and regulatory setting for healthcare and privacy can vary significantly between countries. Additionally, we will exclude articles published before 1996 since HIPAA was not enacted before that year.

Within the MeSH search, I used Boolean search, a style of search that combines keywords with operators "AND", "OR", and "NOT" to produce more relevant and accurate search results. While the "NOT" operator can be used to exclude specific terms from search results, it wasn't utilized in this search because there wasn't a key term explicitly intended for exclusion.

How do these laws encourage greater participation and trust in the healthcare system through the protection of a patient's private health information?

The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) in the United States establishes strict confidentiality standards for patient health information. Promoting this allows patients to be assured that their sensitive health data will be kept confidential, allowing trust in healthcare providers and systems.¹⁹ Patients may be protected from discrimination based on their medical information under privacy laws. Individuals are more likely to seek healthcare if they are confident that their health status will not be used against them. This is their window of opportunity.²¹ Many inmates are from underserved communities, and correctional health services may be their only source of medical care. When compared to non-offenders, incarcerated offenders have a much higher prevalence of some chronic diseases, substance abuse, and mental health issues. Testing them upon entry and treating them while incarcerated, can reduce medical costs in the long run.^{11,14-16} Early tests and initiating treatment can enhance health outcomes by minimizing the severity of illnesses and reducing their transmission to others. HIPAA establishes a framework for holding healthcare entities accountable for breaches or unauthorized disclosures of health information. Knowing that there are legal consequences for privacy violations reassures patients and strengthens their trust in the healthcare system.^{5,6}

How does HIV segregation increase stigma and discrimination against inmates?

Segregation based on HIV status labels individuals and makes their HIV status visible to others. This labeling can lead to the stigmatization of HIV-positive inmates, potentially creating negative perceptions among fellow inmates.^{13,23} Discrimination involves unfair or prejudicial treatment of individuals or groups based on their perceived differences, while stigma refers to the negative attitudes, beliefs, and stereotypes associated with a particular characteristic, condition, or trait that seems "taboo".¹⁷ Identifying stigma raises awareness about negative attitudes and stereotypes associated with specific groups. Being aware of this is the first step toward dealing with and changing discriminatory beliefs. Segregation can undermine efforts to educate inmates about HIV prevention, treatment, and care. By isolating individuals based on their HIV status, there is a missed opportunity to promote understanding, empathy, and accurate information within the inmate population.²¹ The practice of separating HIV-positive inmates has been abolished since 2013 with South Carolina being the last state to do so.⁹ As mentioned in the

United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime's Policy Brief, there is no evidence that HIV segregation is an effective way to prevent the spread.^{22,24}

HIV Staff Survey Stigma vs. Discrimination

One of the scholarly articles I found on PubMed, focuses on HIV stigma in prisons and jails, specifically among correctional staff. The study includes 218 correctional staff members from 32 US facilities and aims to explore their attitudes toward HIV stigma. The study's goals are to provide an overview of staff's level of stigma, conduct psychometric analyses of two stigma mechanisms (prejudice and discrimination), examine differences in stigma attitudes among various staff types, and analyze differences between prison and jail staff. The prevalence of HIV in prisons and jails is significantly higher than in the general population.¹⁰ However, many correctional facilities do not follow CDC guidelines for HIV testing, prevention, or treatment, which can lead to undiagnosed infections and inadequate access to antiretroviral therapy. Stigma can be a barrier to expanding and improving HIV services in these settings.

This study uses the HIV Stigma Framework (HSF) to examine the HIV stigma and stigma attitudes among correctional staff, differentiating between prejudice and discrimination. The research identifies and modifies potential sources of stigma among correctional staff to improve healthcare for inmates and reduce the incidence of infectious diseases. The study also examines differences in stigma attitudes among various staff types and settings (jail vs. prison).¹⁷ 15 questions were asked, focusing on prejudice and discrimination. Exploratory factor analysis was used to assess the factor structure of the stigma measure, and subgroup comparisons were performed to determine if stigma attitudes vary by setting and staff type.¹⁷ Figures 1-9 display 9 of 15 results of the survey. Looking at the pie charts, most staff had positive attitudes, but a few expressed discriminatory ideas, and a few expressed judgmental views. In Figure 1, the question "If people associate or interact with a person who has HIV/AIDS, they may be influenced to participate in immoral or illicit activities", 73% of staff responded with strongly disagree and 2% of staff responded with strongly agree. The study suggests that even the slightest level of stigma can negatively affect inmate behavior and willingness to access HIV services.¹⁷ While the study had some limitations, it contributes to our understanding of HIV stigma in correctional settings. It also highlights the need for interventions to reduce structural and cultural barriers, improve staff education and training, and encourage inmate access to HIV services.

Conclusion

The Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) plays a crucial role in safeguarding the privacy of individuals' health information, including those within correctional facilities. HIPAA regulations must be implemented in these settings while maintaining a balance between security and the right to healthcare privacy. The principle of Minimum Necessity guides covered entities in requesting only what is necessary for Protected Health Information (PHI), promoting a standard for protecting and securing PHI.

Healthcare providers, health plans, and clearinghouses must conduct risk assessments to identify vulnerabilities in the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of PHI. While HIPAA allows for the disclosure of PHI in limited circumstances such as treatment and law enforcement, the emphasis on minimum necessity reinforces the need to restrict access to relevant information.

The stigma surrounding HIV-positive inmates and the consequences of segregating them within correctional facilities not only violates human rights but also breaches guidelines for managing HIV in prisons. This practice not only violates human rights but also breaches guidelines for managing HIV in prisons. The study on HIV stigma among correctional staff, as discussed, emphasizes the importance of addressing prejudice and discrimination to improve healthcare services for inmates and reduce the incidence of infectious diseases. HIPAA also has some positive impacts in encouraging greater participation and trust in the healthcare system by protecting patients' private health information. Patients, including those in correctional facilities, are more likely to seek healthcare if they trust that their health status will remain confidential, reinforcing the framework established by HIPAA. By challenging stigma and discrimination, correctional facilities can create an environment that promotes understanding of HIV, contributing to better health outcomes for inmates.

If people associate or interact with a person who has HIV/AIDS, they may be influenced to participate in immoral or illicit activities

Strongly Disagree Disagree No Opinion Agree Strongly Agree

People living with HIV/AIDS should be treated the same by health care professionals as people with other illnesses (R)

Strongly Disagree Disagree No Opinion Agree Strongly Agree

A person with HIV/AIDS should be allowed to work with other people (R)

Strongly Disagree Disagree No Opinion Agree Strongly Agree

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

References:

1. Initiative PP. States of incarceration: The global context 2021. Prison Policy Initiative. Accessed December 5, 2023. <https://www.prisonpolicy.org/global/2021.html>.
2. Schachat AP. What is HIPAA and what effect may it have on our journal? *Ophthalmology*. 2003;110(6):1074-1075. doi:[10.1016/S0161-6420\(03\)00252-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-6420(03)00252-5)
3. Health Insurance Portability and accountability act of 1996 (HIPAA). Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. June 27, 2022. Accessed December 5, 2023. <https://www.cdc.gov/phlp/publications/topic/hipaa.html>.
4. Bednar AL. HIPAA's impact on prisoners' rights to healthcare. Houston: Houston Journal of Health Law and Policy. 2003.
5. Abernathy C. Corrections and reentry: Protected health information privacy framework for information sharing. Lexington, KY: Council of State Governments, American Probation and Parole Association. 2014
6. Goldstein MM. Health Information Privacy and Health Information Technology in the US Correctional Setting. *Am J Public Health*. 2014;104(5):803-809. doi:[10.2105/AJPH.2013.301845](https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2013.301845)
7. Petrila J, Fader-Towe H. INFORMATION SHARING IN CRIMINAL JUSTICE—MENTAL HEALTH COLLABORATIONS: Working with HIPAA and Other Privacy Laws. 2010.
8. Are you a covered entity? CMS.gov. Accessed December 5, 2023. <https://www.cms.gov/priorities/key-initiatives/burden-reduction/administrative-simplification/hipaa/covered-entities>.
9. McLemore M. *Sentenced to Stigma: Segregation of HIV-Positive Prisoners in Alabama and South Carolina*. Human Rights Watch; 2010.
10. Data and statistics about correctional health. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. April 24, 2023. Accessed December 5, 2023. <https://www.cdc.gov/correctionalhealth/health-data.html>.
11. Gideon L. Bridging the gap between health and justice. *Health Justice*. 2013;1(1):4. doi:[10.1186/2194-7899-1-4](https://doi.org/10.1186/2194-7899-1-4)
12. Davis C, Cloud D. *Bridging the Gap: Improving the Health of Justice-Involved People through Information Technology*. Vera Institute of Justice; 2015.
13. Frank JW, Wang EA, Nunez-Smith M, Lee H, Comfort M. Discrimination based on criminal record and healthcare utilization among men recently released from prison: a descriptive study. *Health Justice*. 2014;2(1):6. doi:[10.1186/2194-7899-2-6](https://doi.org/10.1186/2194-7899-2-6)
14. Sethuram C, Helmer-Smith M, Karunanathan S, Keely E, Singh J, Liddy C. Electronic consultation in correctional facilities worldwide: a scoping review. *BMJ Open*. 2022;12(8):e055049. doi:[10.1136/bmjopen-2021-055049](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-055049)
15. Butler B. Health Information Exchange And Jails. *Health Affairs*. 2015;34(6):1069-1070. doi:[10.1377/hlthaff.2015.0456](https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2015.0456)
16. Fox AD, Anderson MR, Bartlett G, Valverde J, Starrels JL, Cunningham CO. Health Outcomes and Retention in Care Following Release from Prison for Patients of an Urban Post-incarceration Transitions Clinic. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*. 2014;25(3):1139-1152. doi:[10.1353/hpu.2014.0139](https://doi.org/10.1353/hpu.2014.0139)
17. Belenko S, Dembo R, Copenhaver M, et al. HIV Stigma in Prisons and Jails: Results from a Staff Survey. *AIDS Behav*. 2016;20(1):71-84. doi:[10.1007/s10461-015-1098-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10461-015-1098-7)

18. Johnson ME, Kondo KK, Brems C, Eldridge GD. HIV/AIDS Research in Correctional Settings: A Difficult Task Made Even Harder? *Journal of Correctional Health Care*. 2015;21(2):101-111. doi:[10.1177/1078345815572347](https://doi.org/10.1177/1078345815572347)
19. Isailă OM, Hostiuc S. Malpractice Claims and Ethical Issues in Prison Health Care Related to Consent and Confidentiality. *Healthcare*. 2022;10(7):1290. doi:[10.3390/healthcare10071290](https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10071290)
20. Ohringer AR, Ezer T, Serota DP. Prison-based harm reduction services are needed to address the dual substance use disorder and infectious disease epidemics in US prisons. *EClinicalMedicine*. 2020;22:100367. doi:[10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100367](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100367)
21. National Commission on Correctional Health Care. The Health Status of Soon-To-Be-Released Inmates: A Report to Congress, Volume 2: (514682006-001). Published online 2004. doi:[10.1037/e514682006-001](https://doi.org/10.1037/e514682006-001)
22. Kinner SA, Young JT. Understanding and Improving the Health of People Who Experience Incarceration: An Overview and Synthesis. *Epidemiologic Reviews*. 2018;40(1):4-11. doi:[10.1093/epirev/mxx018](https://doi.org/10.1093/epirev/mxx018)
23. HRSA's Ryan White HIV/AIDS program. Accessed December 6, 2023. <https://ryanwhite.hrsa.gov/sites/default/files/ryanwhite/resources/hrsa-justice-tep.pdf>.
24. HIV prevention, treatment, care and support for people who use ... United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. 2009. Accessed December 14, 2023. https://www.unodc.org/documents/hiv-aids/publications/People_who_use_drugs/19-04568_HIV_Prevention_Guide_ebook.pdf.